

SPECIFICATIONS FOR PROPER SPEECH ETIQUETTE AS AN APPARATUS FOR
CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Annotation. The article examines speech etiquette in intercultural communication and highlights the rules of speech etiquette of different cultures. The peculiarities of speech etiquette of different peoples at such stages of communication as greeting and farewell are revealed, and the specifics of maintaining a conversation with the help of questions and wishes are also considered.

Keywords: speech etiquette, speech etiquette formulas, speech rules etiquette, intercultural communication.

Introduction. In every society, there exists its traditions and rituals of communication. The experience of nations, reflected in the original customs and ways of life of different peoples, is preserved in the system of language, speech activities, and established communication formulas. In its entirety, all of this forms etiquette behavior, and in terms of speech, it forms speech etiquette.

Speech etiquette represents a system of means and methods of expressing the relationship between communicators. N.I. Formanovskaya, who has devoted a considerable amount of work to the study of speech etiquette, offers the following definition: "Speech etiquette is understood as regulating rules of speech behavior, a system of nationally specific stereotypical, stable communication formulas accepted and prescribed by society for establishing contact between interlocutors, maintaining and terminating contact in a chosen tone".

Speech etiquette has its national peculiarities. Communicating with representatives of another culture can lead to misunderstandings if one does not learn the rules of speech etiquette. Being in a foreign country, you can inadvertently find yourself in an awkward situation if you are not familiar with the life and communication peculiarities of the local population. This work aims to provide an overview of the variety of speech etiquette formulas, knowledge of which can help resolve misunderstandings that may arise during cross-cultural interactions.

Etiquette rules, for example, in the Russian language, involve maintaining conversation even with strangers if you happen to be in a confined space with them (in a train compartment), while the Japanese and the English will try to remain silent in similar circumstances or talk about highly neutral topics. To avoid awkward or humorous situations in communication with foreigners, it is advisable to familiarize yourself with their etiquette rules in advance. Differences are expected from the very first moment of interaction – greetings. The greeting stage is one of the most important in establishing contact; words should be spoken with sincere intonation, with an infusion of positive emotionality. The specifics of greetings vary among different nations¹.

Even in our culture, there are special greetings for different occasions, different times of day, and different people. In addition to the traditional "hello," we say in Russian, "good morning," "good day," and "good evening." We welcome guests with "welcome" or "please, come in." Slavic brothers from neighboring countries also greet with words like "Здоровеньки

¹ З. Кузнецов И.Н. Деловой этикет: учебное пособие. – М.: НИЦ ИНФРА-М, 2014. – 348с.

булы" and "Ласкаво просимо." The ancient "исполать" (glory to you) and the epic "Гой еси!" have become part of passive vocabulary. Just like in our culture, other cultures also have their unique ways of greeting. For example, among the Ossetians, Abkhazians, and other peoples of the Caucasus, there are about thirty different greetings specialized according to the situation, age, and gender. Therefore, before starting a conversation with the hospitable people of the Caucasus, it's important to assess the situation and choose appropriate words.

Similarly, there is a great variety of greetings among Mongolians, which vary depending on the season. For example, in the fall, they might inquire, "Is the livestock fat?" While in winter, they might ask differently, "How are you wintering?" And by the end of winter, you might hear something like, "Are you welcoming spring well?"

In some Native American tribes, greetings are truly philosophical. They might say, "You are my other self," a tradition that dates back to ancient times when psychoanalysis was unheard of. Although such a greeting might seem unusual to us at first glance, it is undoubtedly pleasant to hear and conveys warmth and love.

Speaking of warm relationships and love, in Polish speech etiquette, there is a special expression for a man to greet a woman: "Целую ручки, пани" (I kiss your hands, madam). However, this expression is not always taken literally and can be used even when the mentioned gesture is not performed.

If we look back at greetings in ancient times, they were noticeably different from modern greetings and might even appear somewhat strange to today's generation. For instance, in ancient Egypt, people would casually ask each other, "How are you sweating?" This sounds quite odd to us and modern Egyptians, but it was considered normal in ancient Egypt.

After the initial greeting, people usually inquire about each other's well-being, health, and family. It's important to remember that each culture has its customs and rules for maintaining a conversation. An interesting conversation style can be observed in Central Asian countries. It's customary to bombard an acquaintance with a series of questions: "How is your health? How are the children? How is your home? How is your car? How is your dog (or other pet)?" Only at the end of these inquiries do they ask about the wife. Specifically, asking about the wife at the end of the conversation allows the husband to ensure that there is no special interest in his spouse, particularly of an intimate nature.

It's worth noting that if you find yourself in England and don't fully understand a local's speech, you should never ask them "Что?" ("What?" in Russian), as you would in our culture. When translated to English, "Что?" becomes "What?" and a polite inquiry turns into a real offense. To avoid coming across as rude, use "sorry" with a questioning tone instead [1, p.487]. In India, as in Nepal, before starting to inquire about someone's health and affairs, they express the wishes "намастэ" (bow to you) and "намасткап" (literally: doing a bow). The tradition of good wishes upon meeting dates back to ancient times. Even the ancient Greeks used to say succinctly and clearly in such cases: "Χαίρε!" (Rejoice!). It's an excellent tradition that fills one with positivity for the entire day. For Romans, it was more important to wish good health upon meeting, which is also quite important and, it must be said, pleasant to hear.

Wishing well is not unique to the people of India and Nepal; it exists in every culture, just expressed differently. For example, in Iran, when meeting an acquaintance, they say: "Да не уменьшится никогда твоя тень!" (May your shadow never decrease!). At first glance, the meaning of these words may not be entirely clear. What does a shadow have to do with it?

However, it turns out to be quite symbolic for these people, as the absence of a shadow indicates impurity taking on a physical form².

Caring Chinese people, upon meeting, first and foremost inquire if their interlocutor has eaten or had lunch. It's not just a formality for them; they genuinely worry about whether their acquaintance is hungry. When the greeting has been successful, questions have been asked appropriately, and wishes have been expressed taking into account the specificity of a particular culture, it's time to consider the nuances of saying goodbye. It might seem like there should be no problems with this, as saying goodbye is not particularly complicated. But it's not always as simple as it seems, as the common "goodbye" is not appropriate in every culture. For example, if you meet someone late at night in England, you should not say "Good night!" to them, as in English, this is not a greeting but a farewell. Of course, in Russia, it's also not quite correct to use the phrase "добррой ночи" (good night) as a greeting. It's more logical to use it when saying goodbye to someone you met late at night. But in our country, this phrase has gradually transitioned from farewells to greetings. This change can be attributed to the fact that in practice, late-night meetings do not happen very often in Russia, as people who used to light their homes with candles typically went to sleep at night. However, in the modern world, with the advent of various late-night broadcasts on radio and television, the situation has changed. Resourceful radio and TV hosts quickly and easily introduced the phrase "Добррой ночи" as a greeting in their speech. Gradually, the phrase has spread to the masses. So today, you can often hear it as a nighttime greeting, despite its incorrect usage, which, to make matters worse, characterizes the speaker as uneducated.

When Chinese people say goodbye, they bow and nod their heads as a sign of respect. People from Beijing often say: "Ужу-и," which means "take care" or "be careful." In general, according to Chinese tradition, when they wish someone well, they advise doing everything slowly. For example, when a guest is leaving, they usually say: "Мань-мань цзоу," which translates to "go slowly" and means "don't rush," "go carefully."

In England, "goodbye" is typically used in formal meetings or as a final farewell, implying "I won't see you again"; whereas "bye" is a more relaxed, informal version. It's also worth noting that if you say "goodbye" with a lowered tone, English people might perceive it as a threat. This emphasizes the importance of not only choosing the right words but also using the appropriate intonation during conversations.

Conclusion. Thus, it has been established that verbal etiquette is an important element of any national culture. It represents a set of verbal forms of politeness that are indispensable. The national specificity of verbal etiquette in each country is extremely distinct because it combines the unique features of the language with the customs, habits, and accepted and unaccepted behavior in social etiquette. Therefore, when communicating with representatives of different cultures, something similar to playing a complex musical instrument occurs. Different registers of communication are activated, and an appropriate tone is chosen in various conditions of complex verbal interactions. And when the right mode is set, it results in that pure, enchanting sound manifested in communication that knows no obstacles or boundaries, ignoring differences in culture, skin color, customs, and morals. As academician N. Moiseev once said, the ancient principle of "love your neighbor as yourself" must be reborn in a new form that aligns with a clear understanding of the necessity of cooperative human

² Antyufeeva Yu.N., Rodionova I.V. Semantic and pragmatic correlation of colloquialisms // Modern European Researches. – 2016. - № 5. – С. 66-69.

activity. This is its main function and purpose. Verbal etiquette will likely continue to evolve in this direction in the future.

REFERENCES:

1. Ремизова В.Ф., Костина Н.Г. Тренинг иноязычного делового общения как инструмент формирования коммуникативной компетентности // Актуальные проблемы торгово-экономической деятельности и образования в современных условиях электронный сборник научных трудов восьмой Международной научно-практической конференции. – Оренбург: Изд-во: Оренбургский филиал РГТЭУ, 2013. – С. 484-509.
2. Белая Е.Н. Национально-культурная специфика коммуникативного поведения представителей разных народностей [Текст] / Е.Н. Белая, В.Г. Болотюк // Психопедагогика в правоохранительных органах scholar - 2014. №2. - 157. Выпуск № 2 (57) / 2014
3. Кузнецов И.Н. Деловой этикет: учебное пособие. – М.: НИЦ ИНФРА-М, 2014. – 348с.
4. Antyufeeva Yu.N., Rodionova I.V. Semantic and pragmatic correlation of colloquialisms // Modern European Researches. – 2016. - № 5. – С. 66-69.
5. Барышева А.Д., Матюхина Ю.А., Шередер Н.Г. Этика и психология делового общения (сфера сервиса): учебное пособие. – М.: Альфа-М, НИЦ ИНФРА-М, 2016. – 256 с.
6. Нестерова Т.Г. Формулы речевого этикета в русском и татарском языках // Филологические чтения: материалы международной научно-практической конференции (декабрь 2014 г.). – Оренбург: ОГУ, 2015. – С.199-207.